

The Role of Social Media in Mobilizing Nigerian Youths during the #EndSARS Protests: Implications for Policy and Activism

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Abstract

The #EndSARS protests in Nigeria, a multifaceted attempt to address some pressing challenges in Nigeria at the time found expression in the unfettered harassment need to address police brutality and advocate for comprehensive policy and policing reforms, witnessed significant mobilization through social media channels. This study investigates how Nigerian youth effectively utilized platforms like Facebook, X (Twitter), WhatsApp, and Instagram to organize and sustain their peaceful protests. By drawing insights from the strategic use of social media during the #EndSARS movement, we explore the impact on government decisions, security policies, and social discourse. Additionally, we consider the abrupt end of the protests and the implications for future social media activism. This research sheds light on the potential of youth-led social media movements to inspire change globally.

Keywords: #EndSARS, Mobilisation, Protests, Social media, Nigerian Youths

Introduction

An essential ingredient of liberal democratic culture is the right to socio-political protest by the people. Protest is organised by the people to demonstrate their displeasure and dissatisfaction to the authorities. This can be targeted against certain programmes, policies, or projects of government or actions of its agents. The assumption is that the contradiction that popular protest catalyzes often results in the dialectical interplay that birth social change, and societal advancement. Despite, its importance, it is not always easy to organize or mobilise people for

protest, especially in societies that are dislocated by many fault lines like ethnicity, religion, regionalism, and so on. Besides, repressive regimes that broker no deal, do not tolerate protests within their political space. To that end, they arrest, molest, and detain protest leaders, and owners or editors of media houses who broadcast or publish issues considered to be sympathetic to the protesters. To circumvent this scenario, modern-day protests are often ignited within the social media ecosystem, due to its capacity to instantaneously disseminate information and integrate people that are separated by geography. Hence social media serve as a veritable instrument of popular political mobilisation. As evidenced in recent years, social media platforms have become powerful tools for mobilization and activism, especially among youth populations. The #EndSARS protests in Nigeria exemplify this phenomenon, as young activists harnessed the digital landscape to advocate for police reform and social justice.

Accordingly, the 2020 #EndSARS protests in Nigeria could not have recorded the level of success it did, without the social media. Social media triggered the protest online through a tweet on X (formerly Twitter) and was used to sustain it offline across the country. This was succinctly captured by Wahab, (2023) when he observed that Nigerian youths leveraged different hashtags to intensify their indignations, the reason for the protest as well as their demand to disband the notorious SARS unit of the Nigerian police. Against this background, the paper examined the varied roles played by social media during the #EndSARS movement, examining how it facilitated communication, organization, and collective action. By analyzing the impact of online mobilization, we shed light on the broader implications for policy, governance, and youth-led activism in Nigeria and beyond especially with the effects of the #EndSARS protest in 2020.

Conceptual clarifications

Social media refers to web-based and mobile technologies that empower users to create and share content (Kaplan & Haenlein, 2010). This fosters interactive dialogue among individuals, groups, and organizations (examples: Facebook, Twitter, YouTube). It can also be a tool for broadcasting information (Cohen, 2009). Social media platforms allow users to participate in online discussions, contribute their own content (blogs, wikis, social bookmarking), and join online communities (Dewing, 2012). These technologies are known for their flexibility, user-friendliness, and ability to be customized. Constantinides and Fountain (2008) view social media as a network that facilitates the exchange of ideas and knowledge. Users can generate,

share, edit, and disseminate information (Biswas et al., 2014). Key features of social media include social interaction, user participation, openness, collaboration, and the ability to use various providers (search engines, blogs, etc.) (Biswas et al., 2014).

Okoro and Nwafor (2013) define social media as interactive platforms that connect users and allow them to share information, opinions, and expertise. They highlight the opportunity for users to connect, share experiences, and collaborate (Okoro & Nwafor, 2013). Narnia and Charl (2011) emphasize that social media allows users to create, share, and search for content without limitations. Sweetser and Lariscy (2008) define it as a "read-write Web" where users actively contribute to content, moving beyond passive consumption. A central theme in most definitions is user-generated participation. This interactive nature distinguishes social media from traditional media, which typically follows a top-down approach to news dissemination (Clark & Aufderheide, 2009).

The following can be regarded as the key characteristics of social media which have made it tick.

1. **Interactivity:** The interactive nature of social media [that comes with Web 2.0 Internet-based applications] is a key characteristic that distinguishes it from the traditional mass media or web 1.0 internet. Anyone could post content online and get feedback or contributions from other users and vice versa. The interactive nature of social media has basically "democratized" the internet.
2. **Accessibility:** Social media is accessible to virtually everyone with a cell phone and internet connection nowadays. They are not bound by location or time as some of the mass media are.
3. **Reach:** The coverage of social media is quite enormous and far wider than conventional mass media as the internet is available on a global scale. Information posted on the internet will travel further than it will do on national TV or news paper.
4. **Adaptability:** Social media platforms lend themselves to great adaptability with many of their inbuilt features like, "Retweet" function in X (Twitter), attachment of photos, short videos to tweets and Facebook posts, links and "favouriting" of tweets. All those features aid the diffusion of information on social media.

5. **Affordability:** Using the social media to broadcast messages is far cheaper than doing same via conventional mass media. Setting up an account is basically free on social media and many users can afford to buy data bundles which are getting cheaper due to competition among the internet service providers.
6. **Mobility:** This is perhaps the most key characteristic of social media. Although social media is accessible from the web, majority of users access it via mobile internet mainly through their cell phones (Akinlade, 2016).

Theoretical Framework

The study adopted the technological determinism theory as its framework of analysis. The theory was coined by Thorstein Veblen, (1857-1929), an American sociologist and economist in the 20th century (Asemah, Nwammuo & Nkwam-Uwaoma, 2017). It was further developed by Marshall McLuhan in 1964. The theory had been used by scholars to explain and analyse group and individual political behaviours. For instance, Nwabunze & Okoye, (2019) used the theory to describe the influence of social media on the voting pattern of youths in Enugu during the 2015 general election. Technological determinism explains how innovation in communication technology helps to engineer some forms of change in society or in the ordering of things. The core message of the theory is the effects technology has on people. Considering that technology shapes the way people think, feel, act, and how society operates. To this end, Baran and Davis, (2012) assert that the theory is a collection of lots of intriguing ideas bound together by some common assumptions. The most central of these assumptions is that changes in communication technology inevitably produce changes in cultural, social, and political order within a society. For instance, the radio requires us to only listen and develop our sense of hearing, television engages both our audio and visual senses. On the other hand, social media engages not just our audio-visual senses. It induces people to participate in an ongoing discussion, and process irrespective of geography and time. This suggests that social networking platforms have revolutionised the way society operates by bringing about a paradigm shift in political behaviour at both individual and group levels. The point to note is that as information and communication technology develops from writing to print, television, computer, and presently social media, social interactions also change with it.

In attempting to relate to analytical utilities of the technological determinism theory to the study, we may raise several questions: Do social media platforms create awareness of SARS

atrocities against youths? Was the social media used to draw attention to the issues, and demands of the protesters? How did social media facilitate youth mobilisation for the protest? What was the global response to information that was shared on social media tweets, chats, and posts regarding the inhuman activities of SARS operatives? Did social media create solidarity among youths during the protests?

The importance of technological determinism theory is that technology has effects on the society. The above assertion is true of social media in our present day; it has affected the lives of the people most especially the youths. Information and ideas on politics and social events are now shared freely on social media space. Again, geography is no longer a limitation when it comes to mobilisation for socio-political protests. Use of social media of various social networking sites and platforms such as facebook, Twitter, Instagram, Youtube, Whatsapp, blogs, and so on, greatly conditions the actions, reactions, perception, and intentions of many youths. Most people today depend on social media platforms and networks for information, on trending issues. This provides sufficient opportunity for social media to condition and direct groups and individual minds and actions on issues.

Methodology

This research explored the role of social media in mobilizing Nigerian youths during the #EndSARS protests of 2020. The methodology relied on a combination of documentary source analysis and literature review. Data was collected from profiles on Social media such as Twitter, Instagram, and Facebook, which included public posts and hashtags related to the #EndSARS movement using Twitter Advanced Search and social media listening platforms. Articles from reputable Nigerian and international news outlets were analyzed to capture the timeline of events, protest narratives, and media coverage of social media's role in the movement. A comprehensive review of existing academic literature was conducted to explore the broader theoretical and empirical context of Social media and social movements, Existing research on youth activism and political participation in Nigeria will be reviewed to contextualize the #EndSARS movement within broader trends. Scholarly articles on the role of media in social change and how communication technologies influence political discourse was also content analysed.

Review of Literature

Social Media as a Tool for Political Mobilisation

Mobilization denotes the process by which political parties, politicians, social movements, activists, and other political and social actors induce citizens to participate in politics to win elections, convince others of their own positions, influence policies and modify rulings (Rosenstone & Hansen, 1999). It has also been seen as the process of galvanizing the people to achieve a given course and fostering their collective consciousness (Akpan & Targerma, 2022, p.230). It, therefore, follows that mobilisation has to do with involvement of people by politically exposed actor(s) to achieve predetermined objectives.

Social media by its nature interacts with other pre-existing socio-economic and political factors within an environment to mobilise people for mass political action and individual engagements. On the scale at which social media has amplified interactions on social media, the entrance of social media has influenced the rate at which these interactions are carried out and the extent of coverage is overwhelming (Irenea, 2017). Historically, social science, and political science literature on social movements and political protests is replete with instances of authoritarian and state repression and/or disruption of these movements. It does this by arresting, prosecuting, detaining, and killing protest leaders/organizers, states also frustrate the planning, organisation, and mobilisation for political protest by censoring, penalizing and closure of media houses that broadcast, or publish articles that are sympathetic to the cause of protesters. In the medieval era, states ceased and burnt several books and manuscripts that were radically oriented. The privatization of telecommunication infrastructure means that states cannot effectively enforce total internet communication eclipse. They can at best restrict the capacity of social activists and human rights defenders (HRDs) to use social media to mobilise people for protest through content censorship and monitoring.

Meanwhile, social media because of its diffuse non-centralised nature is usually difficult to regulate and/or control. Hence, leaders of protest groups in contemporary times leverage its potentials to organise and mobilise citizens for mass political actions. Brever, (2012, p.4) observed that social media (Information Communication Technology, writ large) enhance mobilisation in three essential ways namely (1) facilitate the formation of a network of digital activists, (2) dissemination of censored information on human rights violation by state actors, and (3) enables the formation of a national collective identity that facilitate intergroup collaboration between the socially and geographically distant segment of the society. In their

separate study Lysenko & Disouse (cited in Kringen, 2012) observed that social media can provide a platform for (1) organizing initial protest activity, (2) expanding of popular base for sustained protest, (3) strengthening an ethos of social solidarity, and (4) building international networks of support.

Although, the science of the use of social media as a tool for mobilisation by protest leaders is not yet settled. However, experience demonstrates that social media influences, and stimulate turn-out at protests. Currently, there appears to be a positive relationship between social media and citizens attitude to protest. The nexus is likely to be the product of the determinism potentials of modern communication technology. Considering that social media through tweets, retweets, likes, comments, hashtags and so on, psychologically prepare the mind of people for social actions. By focusing on and persistently highlighting as issue, social media sustain the momentum through jingles, messages, images, voice notes (VN), and videos. Sharing videos of successful protests elsewhere on social media timelines, threads, and statutes triggers a demonstrative effect in another place. The instantaneous character of social media establishes unity of purpose among people at different locations. Moreover, social media permits an expanding use of microtargeted communication that are directed at specific individual or group of people.

Drivers of the EndSARS Protest

Unlike the initial SARS unit, the Nigerian police were generally admired and congratulated by all and sundry for their gallantry, fearlessness, quick response, and meticulous work ethic. The SARS against whom Nigerian youths protested was the direct opposite of the glorious past. They were accused of various acts of misconduct and illegal operations. It was alleged that SARS operatives extorted, detained, and tortured Nigerians, especially youths into confessions, and admittance of crimes they did not commit to save their lives. Observers and commentators on policing in Nigeria have argued that SARS operatives have no regard for human rights. Evidently, a June 2020 report by Amnesty International indicated that between January and May 2020, SARS operatives were involved in about 82 incidences of extra-judiciary execution, dehumanisation, and torture.

Aside from its brutality, SARS operatives deviated from their primary responsibilities of combating violent crimes like armed robbery, illegal possession and use of firearms, kidnapping, car snatching and so on, to intervening in civil matters. The institution deteriorated

to the point of serving as an instrument of debt collection, settlement of interpersonal disputes, relationship quarrels, communal land disputes, and several civil matters against criminal offences. Instead of focusing on its statutory mandate, SARS on account of what many have referred to inordinate quest for material wealth, transformed themselves into moral police. Under this new role, they harass, arrest, abuse, and detain young boys because of their dress and appearance. Worse still, the mere ownership and possession of flashy electronic gadgets such as iPhones, laptop, flashy cars and so on, qualify young Nigerians for forceful arrest, and interrogation. Corroborating this, Eniola, (2022) observed that:

The Special Anti Robbery Squad was created for the purpose of tackling the issue of armed robbery and kidnapping in Nigeria. This unit has been criticized for losing its priorities for killing innocent citizens who are perceived to be perpetrators because of their appearances such as having dreadlocks, wearing crazy jeans and durags, and having earrings on among the male youths and also owning valuable assets like iPhones, cars, MacBook and laptops.

To them, any youth that appears wealthy is a criminal. Consequent upon this labelling and criminalisation, young boys that tint their hair, wear earrings, have dreadlocks, and so on, are classified and treated as ‘Yahoo boys’ (fraudsters). To that end, SARS operatives illegally searched the content of youth laptops and phones. An act that contravenes the positions of the Police Chiefs that security operatives lack the power to search the content of a citizen’s phone. Interestingly, any hapless youth in whose account a large sum of money was discovered is compelled to surrender all or a greater percentage of the total amount to secure their release. Extortion was taken to the next level when SARS operatives were accused of moving around with Point of Sale (PoS) machines for ease of electronic money transfer. While others were dragged to branches of Banks’ Automated Teller Machines (ATMs) for withdrawals. Failure to do so often resulted in endless incarcerations in SARS cells. Besides, it was alleged that there had been several cases of missing persons, forced disappearances, and disappearance of citizens in SARS custody.

Consequently, Nigerians clamoured for and demanded an end to arbitrary arrest, illegal detention, torture, excessive use of force to extract confessions or information, disappearance and so on in the hands of SARS. Each time, there was an outcry against brutality by the SARS, the authorities promised to reform and restructure the police including SARS but nothing was

done at the end of the day. For instance, in 2016 the EndSARS campaign was launched on X (formerly Twitter) by Segun Awosanya because of brutality. In 2017, thousands of Nigerians petitioned the National Assembly on the need to disband SARS. It was at this point that the hashtag #EndSARS gained traction in social media specifically X (Twitter). The intensification of the protest followed a tweet on social media about the killing of a young man in Ughelli Delta State by SARS operatives, who pushed his dead body out of the car and drove off with his Lexus SUV. The handler “@AfricaOfficial2” tweeted saying:

SARS just shot a young boy dead at Ughelli, Delta State as we speak. In front of Wetland hotels. They left him dead on the roadside and drove away with the deceased Lexus jeep. I have videos (Eniola, 2022).

Combined with the preexisting incendiary dissatisfaction, and indignation youths especially boys who have mostly witnessed the brunt of SARS's arbitrary, repressive, and abusive actions took to the streets to demand immediate disbandment of SARS on October 3, 2020 (Adisa, 2021, Abosede, 2020). The street protest started in Lagos, and like wildfire spread to other states, especially in southern Nigeria within days. The protest brought together youths, celebrities, and activists, all of whom had been suspicious, and critical of the activities of SARS operatives.

All these results in *SARSphobia*, hatred, discontent, and negative perception of the Police formation. It was only a matter of time before the bottled-up anger and angst of the majority of citizens against it exploded. The question is not whether the people distaste SARS because of its many atrocious acts. Rather, it was a question of when the people's anger would boil over.

Moreover, there is a demonstrative effect dimension to the EndSARS protest. Shortly, before the EndSARS protest, the United States was occupied by the hashtag #blacklivesmatters protesters over police brutality that led to the deaths of Breonna Taylor and George Floyd. It can be argued that the popularity of the #blacklivesmatters protest on the social media may have influenced the Nigerian hashtag #EndSARS protest. Considering that both protests leveraged social media to create awareness and globalize their campaigns against police brutality and impunity, the successful campaign was partly also due to the ban on Twitter at the time, and many had to depend on the use of proxies, which aided the reach of the messages coming out Twitter NG.

Social Media and 2020 EndSARS Protest in Nigeria

Social media platforms have transformed, modified, and shifted youth behavioural patterns from the need to share it to the need to share in it. To that end, millions of Nigerian youths during the 2020 EndSARS protest were not satisfied by merely sharing the videos, jingles, clips, music, commentaries, news, pictures and so on, about the demonstration. Rather, they decided to feel the need to participate in the protest. The EndSARS protesters exploited the basic features and opportunities offered by social media to articulate, plan, and execute the demonstration. Several meetings and conversations regarding the protest were held on various social media platforms. Using the power of social media, participants in the protests were able to determine and settle the question of who gets what, when and how at every point in time. Every day, protesters identify, and disseminate where to gather and take off point through social media platforms, which made it easy for intending participants to locate and join the group. It was also used to provide guide and direction regarding routes that the protest will take to enhance easy of movement.

Finance constitutes a fundamental requirement for a successful protest. The availability of financial resources encourages and sustains the moral firmaments of protesters. Consequently, the EndSARS protesters leveraged social media to crowdfund and source funds for their activities. For instance, the Feminist Coalition raised about US\$400,000 through crowdfunding in social media. The money was used to tackle several pressing needs of the protesters such as payment of hospital bills, purchase of food, medical supplies, assistance to families of deceased protesters, legal services, and so on. Social media facilitated the instantaneous dissemination of information to millions of youths protesting at various locations across the country, and beyond. It made easy for protesters to easily access valuable piece of information and directions from the others. Indeed, it made it possible for those at Asaba to capture and replicate what those in Benin and other places were doing at every point in time.

Based on the deterministic capacity of communication technology, which social media is an integral part of, ensured that youths are fully conscientised and mobilised for action. The constant highlighting and projection of various forms of brutality, violation, and inhuman treatment of Nigerians, and youths by operatives of SARS, reinforced the passion of youths to participate in the protest. Moreover, youths were convinced that if something was not done very fast, soon every one of them would become victims of SARS brutality, and jungle justice.

This suggests that the news feed from social media justified the essence of the protest in the consciousness of the people.

Moreover, social media amplified the voice of the protesting youths. The amplification would not have been possible under conventional instruments of mass media that are strictly regulated and controlled by the state and its agents such as the National Broadcasting Cooperation (NBC). As expected, the voice amplification resulted in the internationalisation of the protest with the hashtag #EndSARS. By persistently pushing the hashtag, several international personalities, hip-hop artists, football stars, celebrities in America and Europe, and Nigerians in the diaspora joined the campaign and clamour for the disbandment of the SARS unit of the Nigeria Police. This is evident in the following tweets:

- ❖ *@YeleSowore- There will be an #EndSARS March in Berlin, Germany on December 10, 2020. please if you live in Germany endeavour to attend! #RevolutionNow*
- ❖ *@bibzyCarter- Today, 24.10.2020. We held our #EndSars Protest in Gottingen, Germany. We stand with every Nigerian to demand good governance and say No to Police Brutality.*
- ❖ *@ECoolOfficial- CHANGE IS NOW!! Atlanta, Thank you to EVERYONE that came out last minute and in the rain! #ENDSARS*
- ❖ *@Gbemisoke- #EndSARS Houston. Southwest Farmers Market parking lot. Bissonnet @ Centre Pkwy. 2 pm. Let's go.*
- ❖ *@asount- Another round of peaceful protests this week in Dallas and Houston against the inhumane treatment of Nigerian citizens. #EndSARS October 21, 2020:*
- ❖ *@Cyndodo_- I am so proud of my Generation... see people showed up... we literally filled the streets of Dallas. #endsars*
- ❖ *@aireyys- I want to lead the #EndSARS protest here in London, who will join me? Nigerians in the Diaspora let's not be silent #EndSARS #EndSarsProtests*
- ❖ *@OgbeniDipo- On 11/10/2020, alongside other young Nigerians, we led an #EndSARS protest in London, UK in solidarity with our fellow citizens back home in Nigeria. We deployed our resources, time, and money to make our voices heard. And indeed, the global media paid attention to #ENDSARS*

- ❖ @ABUJAPLUG- #SARSMUSTEND *Peaceful Protest in Abuja. Date: Monday, 12th October, 2020, Time: 6am, Venue1: Berger Roundabout (Under the bridge), Venue2: City Gate, Abuja*
- ❖ @UnclePamilerin- *If you are around Akoka or Yaba, we lend our voice today. 11am Unilag Gate. #Endsars #EndSarsProtest #EndSarsNow*
- ❖ @vobevibes- *Tomorrow 11 AM Unilag gate. If you live around let's do this together. Let's lend our own voice to this menace that's eating deep into our lives #ENDSARS*
- ❖ @FakhuusHashim- *There are protests in Jigawa on Monday in Birnin Kudu. #EndSARS*

The protesters also leveraged the various features of social media to request, donate, purchase, and distribute food items and some other social welfare packages. They equally used to locate, hire, and deploy medical doctors to treat those that were sick among them, as well as lawyers to bail and represent arrested protesters in court. Massive protest by the people is naturally a nightmare to the establishments that will always seek means to bring discredit, disorganise, and dismantle popular protest and resistance. To that end, participants in the protest used social media to warn and provide threat assessment reports to guide themselves. All these demonstrate that social media platforms were utilised to coordinate the protest.

Implications for Policy and Activism in Nigeria

At the height of the

1. Government policy and decision-making must improve and evolve – The #EndSARS protests was intended as a peaceful protest that saw a young population show dexterity in the use of social platforms to raise awareness, coordinate actions, and connect with volunteers globally, the response from the government to the demands of the protesting youths showed a poor understanding of the changing nature of social mobilization and the means through which it could be achieved. However, the poor handling of the protest was a stark display of ignorance and an unwillingness of a government to adapt, but use archaic methods to tackle modern challenges.
2. Social media activism is here to stay – The strategic use of social media during the #EndSARS movement demonstrated its potential as a tool for citizen mobilization and advocacy. This as seen in the scale of the protests which was as a result of the ways in

which information was disseminated in a decentralized yet consistent manner which was able to inspire an unprecedented acceptance and turnout of youths in their numbers due to the messaging and the medium. The impact of the protest cannot be diminished even though it ended abruptly, with questions still been raised regarding the nature and character of the Nigerian State and how they influenced the outcome. Despite all the methods deployed by the government to crack down on social media, ban, use of security agents to hunt down and arrest social media users, and so on, has not diminished the spirit shown in 2020. The Nigerian youth have shown rare resilience that is not commonplace when it comes to the fight for rights.

Conclusion

This study investigated the critical role social media played in mobilizing young Nigerians during the 2020 EndSARS protests. Despite years of harassment and brutality by SARS officers, including unlawful arrests, extortion, and extrajudicial killings endured by young people with little resistance, a single tweet on social media was enough to spark widespread outrage and calls to disband the unit. Social media platforms became a powerful organizing tool. They were used to: Coordinate meeting points for protestors. Crowdfund resources to support the movement. Organize medical and legal aid for protestors. Source essential supplies like food and water. Social media also played a key role in garnering international support and sympathy for the cause. Tweets and posts from celebrities, diplomats, and influencers worldwide helped amplify the message of the protestors. Also, the study highlights how social media was used to pressure the Nigerian government. By sharing graphic images and videos of SARS's brutality, protestors used social media to expose the unit's atrocities and force the government to act, despite initial resistance to their demands.

The study reveals that social media played a crucial role in mobilizing and motivating young Nigerians to participate in the #EndSARS protests. This technology significantly altered the attitudes and actions of many young people, transforming them from passive information sharers to active participants in the movement. The large gatherings of youth across major cities, particularly in southern Nigeria, during the protests highlighted a shift away from simple information sharing. These young people felt compelled to take a more active role in fighting for and building a better Nigeria.

References

- Abosede, G. (2024). The roots of the #EndSARS protests in Nigeria. <https://www.washingtonpost.com/outlook/2020/10/25/roots-endsars-protests-nigeria/>
- Adisa, H. (2021). Protests in Nigeria: The Influence of Social media case study: The End SARS Protests in Nigeria. <https://globalhistorydialogues.org/projects/protests-in-nigeria-the-influence-of-social-media/#author>
- Akinlade, A. O. (2016). The influence of social media on the voting behaviour of the youth in South East Nigeria. A research dissertation submitted to the school of postgraduate studies, University of Nigeria, Nsukka in partial fulfillment of the requirements for an award of masters' degree in Mass Communication.
- Akpan, E.B. & Tarerma, T. S. (2022). Social media, mass mobilisation and national development in Nigeria: Lessons from the #EndSARS protest. *ASEAN Journal of Community Engagement*, 6(2),228-243.
- Asemah, E. S., Nwammuo, A. N., and Nkwam-Uwaoma, A. O. (2017). *Theories and models of communication*. Jos: Jos University Press.
- Baran, J. S., & Davis, D. K. (2001). *Mass communication theory: Foundations, ferment and future*. (Third edition) Belmont, CA: Thomson Wadsworth.
- Biswas, A. Ingle, N. and Roy, M. (2014). Influence of social media on voting behavior. *Journal of Power, Politics & Governance*, 2(2), 127-155
- Breuer, A. (2012). The role of social media in mobilising political protest: Evidence from the Tunisian revolution. *Discussion paper*. German Development Institute.
- Cohen, L. S. (2009). Is there a difference between social media and social networking? <http://lonscohen.com/blog/2009/04/differencebetween-social-media-and-social-networking>
- Eniola, A. D. (2022). The impact of social media #EndSARS Nigerian youth activism for police accountability in Nigeria. <https://www.grin.com/document/1336698?lang=en>
- Ireola, K. O. (2017). Use of Social Media in the Generation and Diffusion of Information during the 2015 General Elections in Nigeria [Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria]. <https://doi.org/10.1017/CBO9781107415324.004>

- Kaplan, A. M. & Haenlein, M. (2010). Users of the world, unite! The challenges and opportunities of social media. *Business Horizons*, 53, 59-68
- Kringen, J. A. (2012). Worldwide: The role of social media in social mobilisation. Institute for Defense Analyses.
- Narnia, B. and Charl, M. (2011). The potential of social media to influence socio political change on the African continent. Africa Institute of South Africa *Briefing. No. 46*, March
- Nwabunze, U. O. & Okoye, A. C. (2019). Influence of social media on voting pattern of Enugu State youths in 2015 general elections in Nigeria. *NTAtvc Journal of Communication*, 3(2), 49-67.
- Okoro, N. and Nwafor, K. A. (2013). Social media and political participation in Nigeria during the 2011 General Elections: The lapses and the lessons. *Global Journal of Arts Humanities and Social Sciences*, 1(3), 29 - 46
- Rosenstone, S. J. & Hansen, J. M. (1993). Mobilisation, participation, and democracy in America: New topics in politics. Macmillan
- Sweetser, K. D. & Lariscy, R. W. (2008). "Candidates make good friends: An analysis of candidates' uses of facebook", *International Journal of Strategic Communication*, 2(3), 175-198
- Wahab, B. (2023). How the #EndSARS movement influenced digital activism in Nigeria. <https://www.pulse.ng/news/local/how-the-endsars-movement-influenced-digital-activism-in-nigeria/yxk7kgr>